

Original Article: Comparison of Marital Satisfaction, Emotional Divorce and Religious Commitment among Nurses and Staff of Ahvaz Government Hospitals

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the present study was to compare marital satisfaction, emotional divorce and religious commitment among nurses and staff of public hospitals in Ahvaz. The sample consisted of nine nurses and staff of public hospitals in the community who were selected by the available sampling method. The tools used in this study were Alason's Marital Satisfaction Questionnaire, Emotional Divorce of Razghi *et al.* and Barati's religious commitment. This research is comparative. The findings showed that employees have more marital satisfaction than nurses, given the average of the two groups. Due to the average of the two groups of nurses and public hospitals employees, they are in the same way in terms of emotional divorce. Given the average of the two groups of nurses, they have a higher religious commitment than employees.

Introduction

Marital satisfaction is one of the factors that play an important role in marital sustainability and the

stability of the family system. There are no marriages in the vacuum. Children are more likely to develop anxiety, depression, behavioral disorders, and physical illnesses. Have you ever stuck in a state of affairs to feel frustrated and

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disabled and know how to behave? Have your spouse ever pushed you to fulfill his desires so that you have been forced and contrary to your desire? If such conditions have been repeated in our lives over and over again, you will need to learn the diet that you can behave properly in such circumstances! Mehrabad, 1

Yemen and Eric Bern's work (1) investigated why single and married people do not benefit from meaningful and joyful relationships. They agreed that many couples could not talk about their problems. They cannot express their wishes in explicit and clear sentences. Carman believes that they need to learn to find their inner feelings and know what he really reads and then express their wishes, and so many of their problems will be resolved. Many young couples have problems because of their lack of familiarity and in some cases insufficient awareness of how to deal with marital and emotional relationships between spouses, which unfortunately become family crises in some cases where the effects It can be seen in problems such as increasing divorce statistics, sex diversity, and so on (2). All couples face problems in their relationships. These issues can be severe or mild, short -term, long -term, and from different causes, couples need to be able to remove barriers and a deal of agreement. Solve and accept their differences. The disruptive couples generally have less positive interactions and respond more to their partner's behavior with textual behaviors. All couples have problems throughout their lives, conflict and conflict between couples appear to be natural and unavoidable, and the necessity of the source of turmoil and late disorders is not. Many couples soon realize that they can not only tolerate the differences they have with their partner, but most of these differences are passionate about them, and because of these differences, the partner is more attracted. They live in their lives and they get more stretching. The couples lose their tolerance over their differences. Couples who interact with their spouses should face aspects of themselves and their partner who have been away from their awareness (2).

Differences can be the source of serious emotional and emotional arousal, and each party

tries to change the other, and because they experience severe emotions and emotions, usually to negative and repressive strategies such as criticizing, criticizing and writing They resort to anger to change their partner, and as their efforts to change another, each of them feels that his behavior is more justified and maintains his position more. It is not merely the differences between couples that cause disturbance in relationships, but rather the way couples respond to the differences that cause discontent with relationships. When couples become more acceptable to these differences, they understand these differences better and reduce the reactionary interactions between them. Mutual negative response patterns such as criticism, the need that accompanies the resignation, the defense of the negative emotions and also keeps negative emotions as the emotional and secure emotional connection becomes more difficult and difficult, recent research. They show that there is no conflict and conflict that leads to divorce, but a decrease in the expression of emotional emotions, the positive emotional connection, and the sensitivity of the couples that predict the collapse of the relationship (3).

Emotional Divorce is the coldness of the relationship between a couple. This problem in a relationship causes disadvantage and reduced positive energy in the family. Couples are lost in each other's peaks and only have a home with an interview they are accustomed to. They have a mentally and physically interfered with each other's red line, each accusing each other in their own backyard. Not understanding each other's behavior and speech, lack of understanding of the mood of the other party, and the end of his partner, and all of them, all give up an emotional divorce in couples' lives. There are no accurate statistics on the extent of emotional divorce, but it can be said that the statistics of emotional divorce in our country are more legal (Ashrafi) emotional divorce usually starts complaining and complaining couples, expectations that expectations that It is said, but it is not met in fact the needs of each other. There is no importance to other needs and desires as if they see each other but they do not hear each other, and this is the beginning of the emotional

divorce. The marital conflict is the next step. Are expressed in a loud and rampant voice and the relative calm gives its place to the eye; The anger that shows itself in a variety of ways. Inner anger turns out loud, throwing equipment and physical treatment with insult and humiliation. After this step, the differences are increasing and the wall of silence between the husband and wife is placed, which means that they are not being heard and not being seen, meaning that each is unable to each other, and everyone goes into their inner world and the other is in their inner world. The other side does not give the work to the point where they only play a house for each other and even separate their sleeping place (4).

Religion is one of the prominent phenomena in recent decades. Studies on the role and function of religion in each of the fields of science are due to the same interest and the turn of the people to spirituality (5) In recent years, increasingly, there are many questions in different fields. The sciences have become. Psychology is also not separate from these effects and has tried to provide appropriate answers in relation to modern tendencies to religion, although these answers are still in view of the psychologist's relationship with the relationship between religion and humans, focusing on various aspects and aspects. . What is the perception of God? What is the image of God and adults of God, and what is the importance of this impression in their lives? What is the relationship between different human issues and issues? How does religious faith work in the development of human personality? What are the differences between religious people in individual and social behavior? And the thousands of new years that psychologists face and want to answer these questions Today, more than ever, we need to think and think about the influence of religious proponents on all human affairs, especially the morale and spiritual. Many scholars and scholars believe that religion has an undeniable effect on the health of the soul and body and other aspects of human life. Carl Gustav Jung says I have treated hundreds of patients in me. Among the patients who live in their half -life (6 years of age) I didn't even see a patient who basically requires a religious tendency in life. I can dare say that each of them was a victim of

mental illness because they did not have what the religions gave to their followers at any time, and their ancestors only returned to religion and religious views. They were fully treated (6).

In a study, Heatd (1) described values as one of the eight major psychological factors in achieving mental health and developed personality. He considers health assessment only at the base of one's value system (7). But some psychiatric theorists have another opinion. Freud writes in a letter to Jung: 'I can only trust one thing from my depth, deeply that I believe that all the foundation of human need for religion is on his inferior helplessness.' Humanity cannot tolerate the birth of a world without a parent, and for the god of balance and the pleasant nature of this, this is the most human being who could imagine beta. Therefore, in this study, we have tried to investigate whether there is a difference between marital satisfaction, emotional divorce, and religious commitment among nurses and staff of Ahwaz medical centers.

The method of selecting this type of research is compared to the type of event. The statistical population in this study was all the staff and employees of public hospitals in Ahvaz in 2015. Statistical sample using the method

Sampling is planned in 100 nurses and 100 employees of public hospitals in Ahvaz. The tools used in this study was one of the Itrich Marital Satisfaction Questionnaire developed by Alson (8). This questionnaire consists of 47 items. The answers to the questions of the death questionnaire by the method of Ligert and in the form of 5 options, I completely agree, I agree, I agree with, I disagree, I disagree and I strongly disagree), which are: 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 points for scores less than 30 indicate severe dissatisfaction, 30 to 40 indicate dissatisfaction, screams between 40 and 60 indicate relative and moderate satisfaction, a score between 60 and 70 indicates severe satisfaction and scores above 70 indicates excellent satisfaction with marital relationships. This questionnaire has a key in which a material is scored in reverse, which are: 1, 2, 3, 5, 9, 10, 17, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 26, 36 and 44 to more than the minimum and maximum points are 47 and 235, respectively.

Elson (9) calculated the reliability of the Marital Satisfaction Questionnaire by Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.92, Soleimani (1994) using 11 married teachers in Bojnourd 0.93. Sharifnia (2009) obtained the reliability coefficient of the above questionnaire through Cronbach's alpha 0.86 and L (10). In the present study, Cronbach's alpha method was used to determine the reliability of the marital satisfaction questionnaire, which is equal to 0.82 for the whole questionnaire, which indicates the optimal reliability coefficients of the questionnaire. Another of the emotional divorce test of Razeghi *et al.* (2008) Using a questionnaire of 22 questions of 5 values (always 1, sometimes 2, sometimes 2, rarely 2 never) to examine the structure of the test from the statistical analysis model with statistical analysis method The main components were used and considering that the criterion was set in parallel to examine and calculate the validity of this issue in the questionnaire, factor analysis method was used to determine the validity of this study. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to evaluate the reliability of the questionnaire and the coefficient for the questionnaire was estimated to be 0.9. In the present study, Cronbach's alpha method is used to determine the reliability of the emotional divorce questionnaire. It has 55,000. Each question has

five results and the Likert score has a score of 0 to 4 and the total score is 100. Classification of scores from 0 to 100 based on four grades, respectively, excellent, good, average and poor, which is in the form of a score of (100-176) excellent religious attitude, (51-75) good (26 to 50) average and (25 down)) Religious attitudes were classified as weak. The validity of this test is obtained through a correlation coefficient with the Albert Vernon and Lindsay test, which is equal to 80. This questionnaire is also used in validation through the method of known groups and the difference between the two normal and religious groups was significant and the difference between the two groups was different. This question has been the case in recent years

Reassessing the reliability of this questionnaire was obtained by Spearman-Brown method equal to 63 and its validity was equal to 0.248. In the present study, Cronbach's alpha method was used to determine the reliability of the religious attitude questionnaire, which is equal to 0.79 for the whole questionnaire, which indicates the optimal reliability coefficients of the questionnaire.

Findings

Table 1: Multi -variable variance analysis results) Manava (on marital satisfaction scores, emotional divorce and religious commitment among nurses and public hospitals staff

Level Meaning) p)	f	DF	DF	The amount of	Name Test
0/0002	11/28	196	3	0/763	Pillai Impact Test
0/0002	11/28	196	3	0/562	Wilks Lambada Test
0/0002	11/28	196	3	0/296	Hotel Field Test
0/0002	11/28	196	3	0/396	The biggest root test

As shown in the tables table, the significant levels of all tests indicate that there is a significant difference between nurses and public hospitals in terms of marital satisfaction,

emotional divorce and religious commitment $f = 11/28, p = 0/003$. To find out the difference, the results of the analysis of the variance in a variable in Manava are presented in No. 1.

Table 2: Variety Analysis Results in the Text of Marital Satisfaction, Emotional Divorce and Religious Commitment among Nurses and Staff Hospital Employees

Level You mean	f	Average Regarding	Degrees of freedom	Total Regarding	Variables
0.0001	24.635	3265.58	1	3265.58	Marital Satisfaction
0.231	1.729	415.61	1	415.61	Emotional Divorce
0.0001	14.652	2151.61	1	2151.61	Religious commitment

As can be seen in table number, there is a significant difference between nurses and public hospitals in terms of marital satisfaction $F_{24/635}$, $p = 0.0001$ In other words, according to the averages of the two groups, employees of nurses are satisfied with satisfaction They are more married. Also, the religion of nurses and public hospitals is not significant in terms of emotional divorce $F_{1/729}$, $p = 0/231$ In other words, according to the average of the two groups, nurses and public hospitals in terms of emotional divorce The conditions of the Prophet are the same. There is a significant difference between nurses and public hospitals in terms of religious $14/65$. $p = 0.0001$ In other words, nurses have a higher religious commitment than employees.

Discussion and conclusion

This study was conducted to compare marital satisfaction, emotional divorce and religious commitment among nurses and employees of medical centers in Ahvaz. The results showed that there is a significant difference between nurses and employees of public hospitals in terms of marital satisfaction. In other words, according to the average of two expensive, employees have more marital status than nurses. Explaining this result, it can be said that marital satisfaction is related to the happiness and enjoyment of relationships between couples and means having a favorable feeling of marriage, which can be considered a psychological situation that does not exist spontaneously. Come on, it requires the effort of every couple. In marital relationships, several factors cause spouses to be satisfied with each other, one of which is communication patterns. Marital relationship is a process in which couples exchange feelings and thoughts verbally and non-verbally. If we pay attention to the factors of marital satisfaction, we can expect that by increasing the level of satisfaction and mental health, many psychological, emotional and social problems will be reduced. By raising the level of marital satisfaction and life satisfaction, people in the community will be able to grow and excel and provide social, cultural, economic, etc.

services with more peace of mind, and families will also benefit from this progress. The core of satisfaction with family and life in general. In fact, it can be said that the health of society and the family depends on people's satisfaction with their marriage. There are more than one hundred published studies that have evaluated the continuity of satisfaction and the strength of couples' relationships.

In recent years, focus on couples and marriage has increased due to the worrying statistics of divorce, and any research in this field can have applied and credible findings so that we can reduce its devastating effects, yet the family There are living and changing essences that organize a flower and spread over time and place by using their members and during the Datsi communication. The family can be considered as an emotional unit and a network of intertwined relationships that are based on the marriage of men and women. And a person's satisfaction with marital life constitutes his or her satisfaction with the family, and the family's satisfaction is in the sense of life satisfaction and thereby facilitates the growth and excellence of the material and spiritual development of society. Marital satisfaction can be considered as a psychological situation that does not occur in itself but requires the efforts of both couples, especially in the early years of marital satisfaction and relationships are the most dangerous in the mosaic. If you pay attention to the factors of marital satisfaction, it can be expected that by increasing the dirty level and mental health, many psychological, emotional and social problems will be reduced. By promoting the level of marital satisfaction and life satisfaction, the community will calmly grow and excellence and social, cultural, economic and services, and families will benefit from this progress. Numerous studies have shown that marital satisfaction has a significant impact on people's mental and physical health (11). Also, the results of Olson *et al.* (1) indicate that people's satisfaction with their marriage is 2 % and with life satisfaction in general. Marital satisfaction is influenced by a set of different factors that none to Tehrani are sufficient to create satisfaction (though these factors can

vary in couples and cultures, these factors of personality, rewarding, belief, communication, emotional, emotional, Social and ... are effective in marital satisfaction. There is no significant difference between nurses and public hospitals in terms of emotional divorce. Emotional is in the same way in the same way. The results of this study are in line with the results of Jalili *et al.* (1), Mollazadeh (1), Ralf and Gallon (1), Clark West (1). Given the averages of the two groups, nurses and patients of the state provinces were in the same way in terms of almost the same in terms of emotional divorce. This relationship leads to the weakness of the emotional relationship of the husband and wife C can have together, such as mental, physical, emotional, and even speech relationship, the presence of this problem in a relationship causes illness and positive energy in the family. Have a home or a school that is used to him. These people, mentally and physically, have identified the red line for each other, and each accuses each other in their own backyard. Not understanding each other's behavior and speech, lack of understanding of the mood of the other party, and the end of his partner, all together to create an emotional divorce in couples' lives. In this hypothesis it was shown that there was no difference between emotional divorce between nurses and employees

There is also a significant difference between nurses and government hospital staff in terms of religious commitment. In other words, according to the averages of the two groups, nurses have a higher religious commitment than employees. The result of this hypothesis with the results of the research of Dehghan Shetha *et al.* (2013), Bakhshipour (2012), Bashiri (2011). Abdollahpour *et al.* (2009), Sandra and Hugai (12). It is consistent. Explaining this result, we can say that today more than ever we need to think about the impact of religious beliefs on all human affairs, especially emotional and spiritual issues. Many thinkers and experts believe that religion has an undeniable effect on the health of body and soul and other aspects of human life. It is therefore necessary, from a pathological point of view, to address the causes of marital incompatibility and unsuccessful marriages, and to examine the role of factors such as personality

traits and religious orientation in marital adjustment and satisfaction, because the existence of a healthy atmosphere in The family is one of the main obstacles to transmitting the positive customs, culture to the next generations. Employees with stronger religious beliefs are better able to cope with stressful situations. They recover faster from illness than non-religious people, experience lower levels of negative emotions and depression, have higher academic performance, have less anxiety, and have higher social support. An inner religious orientation is, in fact, an all-encompassing motivational commitment. Thus, religion is an obligation for a person with an inner religious orientation that motivates and is the source of all his external thoughts, moods and behaviors. In other words, everything that a person does and is doing is related to his religious belief. His religion and religious affairs are the source of all his life motives. That a person breathes, eats, sleeps, gets married, and so on, is entirely because of his or her chosen commitments. These factors can affect mental health and increase self-confidence and motivation, including those related to academic achievement. Religion can intervene in the initial stages of life-threatening factors and the existence of a person, and as a The mediator acts. It can also play a decisive role in the re-evaluation process and after the problem has occurred, creating more hope and meaning for Julie. In addition, religion in the interpretation of events can affect the results and consequences of stressors. Those with a stronger religious orientation are better able to moderate stressors and, as a result, have better mental health. In fact, believing in a God who is by man's side at all times and holds his hand in hardships and poverty and helps him, will give man hope for life. In the event that he faces difficulties such as illness, he will stand firm and use all his strength. Such a person is definitely in a good position in terms of mental health.

Because religion is the true religion that has always been with mankind. As the main pillar of any culture, it strengthens and strengthens society. Maintaining this relationship with God brings peace to the individual that prevents the balance of man from being upset, and also

shapes the worldview of the structure of moral values. As a result, having balance in life and paying attention to moral values, which are manifested in the form of desirable traits in people's behavior, give meaning to people's lives and lead to their mental health. Ultimately, from this point of view, the meaning of life is not possible except in the light of faith in God and religious practices, which have the value of high providence in making life meaningful and feeling satisfied with life.

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